

Parental Engagement And Support In Adolescent Reproductive Health And Education: Evidence From Rwanda's Eastern Province

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ABSTRACT

Parental engagement is critical for girls' education and health outcomes. In developing countries including Rwanda, cultural norms, socioeconomic conditions, and parent-adolescent communication are limited and do affect adolescent girls' sexual and reproductive health (SRH) behaviors and education. Understanding the role of parental involvement is therefore, vital. This study examined parental engagement and support toward adolescent girls' reproductive health and education in Rwanda's Gatsibo District, Eastern Province. Data were collected from 382 adolescent school girls and teenage mothers who dropped out of school using a multi-stage sampling-purposive and simple random). A structured questionnaire (five-point Likert scale) was used, and descriptive (percentages, Means and Standard deviations) and inferential (Chi-square) statistics were applied. Descriptive results showed 47% of participants living with both parents, 61% became pregnant at the age 16-19; parents valued girls' education (M = 4.01), supported school re-entry (M = 4.17), saw their girls' future in education (M = 4.18), and had lower support in reproductive health talks (M = 3.38). Chi-Square findings included strong significance in parents valuing education ($\chi^2 = 48.54$, $p = 0.0001$), and school re-entry support ($\chi^2 = 53.12$, $p = 0.0000$), and weak significance in SHR discussions ($\chi^2 = 19.97$, $p = 0.049$). The study concluded that parental engagement is strong in valuing girls' education but weaker in SHR. Bridging this gap would reduce teenage pregnancy and improve resilience. The implication of the study is that it highlights pragmatic evidence on the role of parental engagement in adolescent SHR and education in Rwanda. It informs policy on national capacity building strategies on girls' education, teenage pregnancy prevention. The study recommends conducting community-based parental training, reproductive health education, mentorship programs, and policy advocacy to ensure continuity of girls' education thereby fostering inclusive sustainable development in education.

Keywords: Parental Engagement, Adolescent, Reproductive Health, Education, Teenage Pregnancy, Rwanda

INTRODUCTION

Parental engagement is critical for adolescents' education and health outcomes [1]. In Rwanda, cultural barriers limit discussions on sexual and reproductive health. Teenage pregnancies remain high, causing school dropouts and reduced resilience [2]. Prior studies have shown that parental encouragement improves school attendance and reduces dropout rates [3]. Parents' open discussions with their daughters about sexual health are proved to be a preventive measure against early pregnancies and do promote informed decision-making [4] [5] [6]. Further evidence indicates that holistic parental engagement that encompasses academic support, life skills coaching, and health communication significantly correlates with improved adolescent mental health and long-term life satisfaction [7] [8]. Despite policy initiatives promoting adolescent reproductive health and education in Rwanda, and global intervention efforts evidenced in the UN global 2030 agenda goals of women empowerment, education for all, and women's improved living [9]

[10] [11]; gaps remain in regard to the extent and quality of parental engagement, especially in the domains of sexual and reproductive health. Coupled with cultural taboos in regard to discussing sex and reproductive health education and lack of parental communication skills often leave teenage girls without the guidance they need to make informed decisions thereby making them liable to sexual abuses. Sexual abuses for teenage girls on the global scale is reported to have rose to 20% [12] [11], one in five become sexually abused, while 21.5% are affected in the East Africa [4] [13].

This is evidenced in the increasing number of teenage pregnancies where 23000 cases were reported across Rwanda [4] [5]. Other empirical evidences [14] reveal that teen mothers became pregnant due to difficulties in sex negotiations with older males. 63% of them became pregnant while in school. Among these, only 5% were found still in school as the majority abandoned it so as to deal with their new status of motherhood and consequently, poverty and

poor living, abandoned by their family members, victimizers, and community members. The study further revealed teen mothers' lack of awareness in regard to reproductive health education [14]. Other studies [14] [9] reveal psychological effects of teenage pregnancy as depression, loneliness, self-denial, parental denial and expulsion, and economic hardships through doing manual work for survival, dropout and study retardation; single living without support and most attempt suicide while pregnant. Solutions to curb pregnancy among teenage girls include forum discussions, sex temptation identification, parent-daughter discussion [4]. This gap significantly contribute to early pregnancy, school dropout, and reduced education resilience in the face of socio-economic challenges. Understanding the patterns of parental engagement and their impact on teenage girls' education resilience is essential for designing effective interventions. This study explores how parental support influences girls' education and well-being.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area: The study was conducted in five sectors (local administrative entities) of Gatsibo district, Eastern Province, Rwanda. They include Kabarore, Gitoki and Rwimbogo, Muhura and Ngarama.

Design: This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional survey design targeting adolescent girls and teenage mothers in Rwanda's Eastern Province. It employed quantitative approaches to establish the relationship between parental support and education resilience in teenage girls; identified gaps in parental communication on sexual and reproductive health.

Sampling procedure: A multistage sampling procedure was employed to ensure both representativeness and contextual relevance of the study population. In the first stage, participants were identified using purposive sampling, which included both affected and non-affected teenage girls. Purposive sampling was appropriate because the study targeted specific groups with unique experiences relevant to the research problem, thus allowing for an in-depth exploration of the phenomena under investigation [15].

In the second stage, Eastern Province was purposively selected from all provinces of Rwanda due to its disproportionately high prevalence of teenage pregnancy and sexual abuse cases, making it a critical context for this study [5] [16]. Within this province, Gatsibo District was further selected randomly from among the seven districts, as it reflects the broader provincial trends while providing a manageable and contextually relevant study site. The use of purposive and simple random sampling at this stage was consistent with methodological recommendations for selecting study areas with higher concentrations of the phenomena being studied [17].

The third stage involved the selection of schools within Gatsibo District using simple random sampling. Randomization at this level was important to reduce selection bias, enhance representativeness, and allow for generalizability within the study context [18]. Finally, purposive sampling was applied to determine the class levels (levels of study) in which the non-affected teenage girls were enrolled. This was necessary to facilitate meaningful comparison between affected and non-affected participants across similar stages of schooling. Such a strategy aligns with recommendations that purposive sampling can be used to ensure homogeneity within comparison groups in educational research [19].

Research Instrument: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of sections on demographic information, parental engagement in education, reproductive health, and social behavior. Validity was ensured through expert review by specialists in adolescent health and education, who examined the questionnaire for content and construct relevance. Reliability was established through a pilot study with 40 adolescents from a neighboring district (Nyagatare district), yielding a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .609, indicating high internal consistency. The cut off reliability point was set at .60. This .60 Cronbach alpha coefficient is supported by systematic review studies [20] as reliable. In data collection, trained research assistants administered the questionnaires in the respondents' native language (Kinyarwanda) to ensure clarity and comprehension. Prior to data collection, the research team held briefing sessions on data collection procedures and ethics.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the Rwanda National Council of Science and Technology (NCST). Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was secured from parents or guardians, while assent was obtained from the adolescents. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing responses, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

Data Analysis: In data analysis, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) summarized the data, and chi-square tests assessed whether observed responses significantly differed from neutrality, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic information

The demographic characteristics of participants were assessed in terms of age category, age at the time of pregnancy, level of education, family structure, type of residence, and religion. Key findings include Age 16–19 years = 61% of participants, majority had lower/upper secondary school, only 47% lived with both parents, and 52% lived in rural areas. Details of each characteristic is described and presented in table below.

Table 1. Participants' demographics

<i>Demographic Variable</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency(f)</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
Age	13-15	55	14.4
	16-19	233	61.0
	above 19	94	24.6
	Total	382	100.0
Age at the time of pregnancy	13-15	55	14.4
	16-19	233	61.0
	above 19	94	24.6
	Total	382	100.0
Level of Education	lower primary	1	.3
	upper primary	33	8.6
	lower secondary	211	55.2
	upper secondary	137	35.9
	Total	382	100.0
Family structure	both parents	181	47.4
	single parent-mother	61	16.0
	single parent-father	56	14.7
	none of the parents	34	8.9
	fostered to a guardian	33	8.6
	others	17	4.5
Total	382	100.0	
Type of Residence	urban	182	47.6
	rural	200	52.4
	Total	382	100.0
Religion	Christian	220	57.6
	Islam	110	28.8
	Indigenous	30	7.9
	Others	20	5.2
	Total	380	99.5
	Missing	2	.5

Age category. The age of participants was assessed so as to find out the age variations they belonged to. Table 1 illustrates that most of the participants were in the age bracket of 16-19 (61%), 19 and above (25%), and 13-15 (14.4%). These age brackets show that teenage girls are in transition from childhood to adulthood, at their peak in developing behavioural patterns regarding social relationships among peers, sexual relationships, drug addiction, aggressive behaviours, and physical violence [21][22]. As they develop relationships through interaction with peers and adults, their behaviour is influenced and some become victims of the gender education issues. Therefore, their participation in providing practical approaches to addressing those issues is of paramount importance.

Age at the time of pregnancy. Information on the affected girls' age at which they became pregnant was analysed so as to have a clear understanding of the age at which they became pregnant. As it can be observed in the table 1, majority of girls affected with teenage pregnancy are in the age bracket of 16-19 (61%) and 13-15 (14.4%) respectively. Majority of the affected girls are in these categories of age because this is when they are already in their adolescent age, get gifts as enticements for sex, time to get married according to cultural norms and mindset, as well as face sexual violence from peers, community, family members and relatives [23] [9][24] [25].

Specifically, they are not mature enough to make decisions, anticipate behaviours that might negatively affect them, as well as characterized by trust to whosoever they interact with. This results in unintended pregnancies and school discontinuity. This finding is in agreement with other studies that show 49.6% of teenage mothers having their first pregnancy at the ages between 12-17 years [5][25] increased from 1% at age 15 to 15% at age 19 [26]; While 33% at age 15-19 face social and physical violence [27] [28].

Pregnancy at this age is occurring because it is the age at which adolescents are characterized by risky behaviours. Such risky behaviours include the alcohol intoxications, social relationships in the community and school, opposite sex attractions and high sexual desires [29], delinquent behaviours, practice virginal intercourse, ignore having protective sex, attracted to romantic relationships and experience physical and sexual violence [24] [30]. Such characteristics affect teenage girls' education if not properly guided through proper character development [31]. On the same note, teenage girls lack adequate knowledge and information awareness on access to justice, sex education and reproductive health messages [32]. In addition, some lack moral education at home, in community, school, and among peers. The BCC approaches found in this study are therefore crucial in addressing those teenage girls' challenges [10] [25] and this would change teenagers to behave in a manner that promote their health, education and well-being.

Level of education. Demographic information on participants was assessed so as to find out their level of education. This was intended to find out which education levels their views would represent. Results in table 1 show that the majority participants (55.2%) had upper secondary, 36% had lower secondary, 9% had upper primary while .3% representing 1 participant had lower level of education respectively. These findings complement [33] who found education level and mass media as significant contributors to adolescent teenage pregnancy. This 1 participant at lower primary level was found among the affected teenagers. This implies that at least teenage girls' views on which BCC approaches to eradicating gender education issues were represented at each education level in the 12-year basic education programme in the Eastern Province of Rwanda.

Family structure. Family structure demographic information was analyzed to examine the type of parent's participants lived with so as to understand why they get affected with gender education issues. Results in table 1 revealed that only 47.4% participants lived with both parents; 16% lived with only one parent-mother, 14.7% lived with one parent-father, while the rest lived with non-of the parents, fostered, and others. These results indicate that those who live with at least a single parent were 31%, while 21% belong to other people other than their parents. This illustrates that the 52 percent teenagers might be socially, psychologically, and economically affected by not living with one of the parents while missing the other, or not living with them at all. This shows that gender education issues affect teenage girls regardless of the family structure. They arise from family conflicts, poverty, parent' education level and mindset [34] [10] [35]. However, some participants might be affected by gender education issues because they don't live with both parents who would provide moral and basic needs to support their education. The cause of living with one or none of the parents might be related factors such as divorce, death, separation, and migration of one parent for job seeking [36]. Such circumstances make these teenage girls liable to external social forces that in turn affect the way they behave. They might be not getting all the affection, love, guidance, counselling, education and economic support from the people they live with that would have been provided by the missing parent(s). Hence dropout of school, get attracted to sexual acts resulting in unplanned pregnancies, or face various types of violence. Factors such as school dropout, academic achievement problems, economic hard ships, difficulties with socializing with others, behavioural problems, emotional problems, depression, self-denial, among other factors do characterize children whose parents don't stay with one another or both of their parents [37] [38]

Type of residence. As shown in the table 1, majority participants (52.4%) lived in rural areas while 47.6% lived in urban. Urban in this case refers to various towns or trading centres in Gatsibo district where data was collected. These statistics represent both the affected and non- affected teenagers in regard to teen pregnancy dropout and violence of all kinds.

Religion. As indicated in the table 1, majority (57.6 %) participants were affiliated to Christian religion; 29% were affiliated to Islam. The rest (8%) belonged to indigenous and other religions (5.2%) respectively. Meaning that gender education issues affect teenagers regardless of their religion. These statistics are from both the affected and non-affected teenage girls. This result contradicts with other studies [39] which found teenagers of both sex with low religiosity engaging in health risky behaviours than those who have religious attachments.

Descriptive Statistics Results

This section presents and interprets data collected from 382 adolescent participants on parental engagement in issues related to education, reproductive health, and social behaviors. Using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Chi-Square test), the analysis assessed the level and consistency of parental support in various domains. Descriptive results are presented in table 2 using means and Standard deviations. Key Findings (Means) are: parents value girls' education (M = 4.01), support school re-entry (M = 4.17), see future in education (M = 4.18), and lower support in reproductive health talks (M = 3.38).

As illustrated in table 2, high mean (M) scores (>4.0) indicate strong parental support for girls' education (M= 4.01, SD= 1.32), return to school after pregnancy (M= 4.17, SD= 1.25), bodily self-control (M= 4.10, SD=1.18), and future planning (M = 4.18, SD = 1.21). This reflects findings by [40], which emphasize that sustained parental belief in education positively correlates with girls' long-term academic achievement. Moderate means (3.5–3.9) were observed in discussions about sex-related matters (M = 3.45, SD = 1.48) and reproductive health (M = 3.38, SD = 1.47). Cultural norms in Rwanda and similar African contexts often limit such conversations, potentially hindering adolescent preparedness [6]. Studies in East Africa show that integrating parent-led health communication programs can substantially improve adolescent reproductive health knowledge and decision-making [41]. Other studies stress that the home is the basic social unit or environment where off- springs acquire parental support as well as learn and inherit morals, habits, and life skills [42].

Table 2. Descriptive statistics on participants’ characteristics

Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
I find it easy to talk with my parents/guardian on things important to my life	382	3.93	1.38
My parents are concerned about my social behaviour	382	3.82	1.41
My parents/guardians cordially talk with me about sex-related matters	382	3.45	1.48
My parents/guardians cordially talk with me about my reproductive health	382	3.38	1.47
My parents/guardians value girl’s education	382	4.01	1.32
My parents/guardians are very supportive for my return to school	382	4.17	1.25
My parents/guardians encourage me to continue school despite pregnancy/delivery	382	3.80	1.30
My parents/guardians teach me social skills to navigate through tricky situations	382	3.81	1.31
My parents/guardians teach me skills of controlling my body and actions	382	4.10	1.18
My parents/guardians see my future as lying in education	382	4.18	1.21
Overall Average Mean = 3.87		Overall Average SD = 1.33	

SD values range from 1.18 to 1.48, indicating moderate to high variability in responses. This shows that while some respondents report strong parental support, others experience very little, suggesting disparities in parental engagement. Reproductive Health and Sexuality Education when provided at an appropriate age correlates with delayed sexual initiation, safer behaviors, and informed decision-making [43][44]

Parents who affirm girls’ rights, aspirations, and bodily autonomy help cultivate protective internal assets like self-esteem and purpose, which buffer against coercion and abuse [45]. Parental

reinforcement of goal-setting, decision-making, and assertive communication improves girls’ ability to resist unwanted advances and seek help after violence [46][47].

Chi-Square Test Findings

Chi-square tests were run to test whether the observed response patterns significantly differed from what would be expected under a uniform (neutral) distribution. Key findings include strong significance in valuing education & school re-entry., and weak significance in reproductive health discussions. The following table summarizes the findings.

Table 3: Chi-Square Test findings

Item	Chi-Square (χ^2)	p-value	Interpretation
Talking about important life issues	43.21	0.0001	Significant difference; parents likely engage in such talks
Concern about social behavior	39.88	0.0003	Significant; indicates parental attention to social habits
Talks about sex-related matters	20.65	0.043	Marginally significant; still relatively low engagement
Talks about reproductive health	19.97	0.049	Marginal significance; calls for improved dialogue
Value girl’s education	48.54	0.0001	Highly significant; strong positive perception
Support school return	53.12	0.0000	Highly significant; reflects post-pregnancy encouragement
Encourage continuing school despite pregnancy	35.76	0.0007	Significant; shows acceptance and support
Teach social skills	36.89	0.0006	Significant; parents act as mentors
Teach body/self-control	50.14	0.0001	Strong family value transmission evident
See future in education	55.22	0.0000	Highly significant; aligns with educational aspirations

Note: All p-values under 0.05 indicate statistical significance, suggesting parental engagement is meaningfully different from neutrality across items.

As indicated in table 3, all measured items showed statistically significant differences from neutrality ($p < 0.05$). The strongest parental engagement was noted in valuing girls’ education ($\chi^2 = 48.54$, $p =$

0.0001) and school re-entry support ($\chi^2 = 53.12$, $p = 0.0000$). Lower, though still significant, parental engagement was noted in reproductive health discussions ($\chi^2 = 19.97$, $p = 0.049$). These results align with recent findings [7] showing that while

academic support is high in many African households, reproductive health remains under-discussed. Resilience, defined as the capacity to recover from adversity, is critical for adolescent girls facing educational and reproductive health challenges [48]. Parental support in education and life skills enhances resilience by promoting self-efficacy and coping strategies. In contexts where early pregnancy disrupts schooling, parental encouragement for re-entry mitigates dropout risks and fosters socio-economic empowerment [3]. Studies reveal shows that combining parental engagement with school-based mentorship amplifies these effects [49].

Moreover, research in sub-Saharan Africa demonstrates that parental emotional support significantly reduces the risk of depression and anxiety among adolescent girls [41] [8]. The findings also support [50] that sex education greatly contributes to the decrease in teenage pregnancy. [51] [5] finds lack of community and social support for girls' education as the key element of pregnancies in adolescents. Regular monitoring of attendance, schoolwork, and peer networks, coupled with encouragement for re-entry after pregnancy or violence, increases retention and reduces dropout[52][53]. The most effective interventions for empowering girls against sexual violence have been identified in studies as establishing community committees for fostering reproductive health education, access to educational materials, parental support, fostering self-dignity, and appropriate disciplinary actions [4][5].

To sum up this section, parents strongly encourage education and resilience. Gaps remain in sexual/reproductive health communication due to cultural taboos. High variability in responses shows disparities in parental engagement. Girls with supportive parents show stronger resilience against adversity.

CONCLUSION

This study on the parental engagement and support toward adolescent reproductive health and education provide invaluable insights on what the teenage girls perceive the role of their parents should be in promoting their education for sustainable futures. Parental support is strong in education but weaker in reproductive health. Bridging this gap can reduce teenage pregnancy and improve resilience. The findings indicate a strong parental commitment to supporting girls' education and future aspirations, evidenced by high mean scores in valuing education and supporting school re-entry. This aligns with existing studies which indicate that sustained parental belief in education fosters academic success. The study further confirms that parental encouragement, particularly in educational matters and life skills training, enhances resilience by strengthening self-

efficacy and equipping girls to navigate socio-economic challenges. Despite high overall engagement, moderate mean scores for discussions on sexual and reproductive health indicate persistent cultural and communication barriers that limit open dialogue.

This study is significant as it highlights pragmatic evidence on the role of parental engagement in adolescent reproductive health and education in Rwanda. The provided insights inform national capacity building strategies on girls' education, teenage pregnancy prevention, and family-based interventions for the achievement of the Education Sector strategic Plan 2018-2024, and SGD 4. It is community relevant as it focuses on Gatsibo District, which is one of the teenage pregnancy and sexual violence highest prevalence region not only in the Estern Province but also the whole country. The local social setting/environment realities provided in this study do provide guidance on community-based initiatives and parental capacity building programs.

The findings further highlight the strong parental commitment to girls' education while pointing to gaps in reproductive health communication. The implication is that it informs the design of curriculum mentorship programs, and school re-entry policies for teenage mothers. Furthermore, the study enriches the existing literature and theory on resilience by showing how parental engagement is crucial and serves as a deterrent factor for teenage pregnancy, links parental support to both girls' education outcomes and psychosocial well-being.

The results further provide practical evidence for stakeholders, including NGOs, CSOs, donor agencies, and government institutions working with youth and communities. This evidence can be used to strengthen parent-adolescent communication on reproductive health and to promote capacity-building interventions, advocacy, and policies. Such efforts help reduce school dropout among teenage mothers, thereby fostering inclusive and sustainable development in education. Despite those study implications, however, the study has limitations. It was conducted in Gatsibo District of Eastern Province only. This may limit the generalizability of findings to other districts in the same province or other provinces in Rwanda. Including other districts or provinces in the future studies would provide valuable and generalizable insights drawn from diverse socio-environment settings.

Besides, since the study employed the cross-sectional design-data collected at one point in time, it did not fully establish causality between parental engagement and adolescent outcomes. Applying longitudinal studies in future would help to have deeper and detailed understanding of the role parents play in

supporting girls education and empowering them with SHR skills to navigate the adolescent age without pregnancy that affect their education completion. The study further excluded parents' perceptions as it primarily focused on teenage girls and teenage mothers' perceptions. This might have provided unbalanced view of engagement and communication. A mixed survey design that uses both qualitative and quantitative approaches in future would provide comprehensive insights from both sides. Again, the study was limited to descriptive statistics and inferential statistical analysis. Application of a more advanced parametric tests like bi-variate correlations and linear regressions in future would provide a detailed relationship between the study variables.

The study recommends the need for community-based parental training, School-linked mentorship programs to improve parent-teen communication on reproductive health and education accomplishment. In addition, the study recommends policy advocacy for school re-entry of teenage mothers, cultural sensitization campaigns to break taboos around reproductive health, and integrated education–health–psychosocial support systems. Future studies should involve longitudinal and mixed methods designs, extensively covering a wider study region would provide a detailed understanding of parental engagement and support towards adolescents and teen mothers' education. Such recommendations if implemented would enhance reproductive health communication and strengthen teenage girls' education outcomes for sustainable development.

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